

Welcome to Editors and Editorial Board Members

The “*Pediatric surgery in Tropics*” takes immense pleasure in welcoming the editors and editorial board members. The following is a brief introduction of these accomplished individuals whose achievements easily exceed several pages. Their collaboration is sure to enrich the exchange of knowledge among pediatric surgeons around the globe.

Sameh Mahmoud Shehata (Patron)

Dr Shehata is Professor and Past-Chairman of the Department of Pediatric Surgery at the Faculty of Medicine, University of Alexandria, Egypt. He was President of the Egyptian Association of Pediatric Surgeons (EPSA), IPEG Middle East Chapter and President of the World Federation of Associations of Pediatric Surgery (WOFAPS). He innovate a technique of laparoscopic orchidopexy (Shehata technique). He is editorial board of many national and international pediatric surgery journals.

Vivek Gharpure (Editor-in-Chief)

Dr. Vivek Gharpure is Professor of Pediatric Surgery at the Rural Medical College, Ahmednagar, India. Formerly he was Associate Professor at MGM Medical College and Government Medical College, Aurangabad. He was Vice President of Maharashtra chapter of Indian Association of Pediatric Surgeons and Convener of Community Oriented Pediatric Surgeons (COPS). He is an avid birdwatcher, marathoner, mountaineer, bibliophile, origami artist and he likes to make mathematical puzzles. He volunteers for two weeks every year to work for charity in pediatric hospitals of South East Asia.

Venkatachalam Raveenthiran (Editor)

Dr. Raveenthiran is Professor and Head of Pediatric Surgery at Government Cuddalore Medical College, Chidambaram, India. Formerly, he was Professor and Head of Pediatric Surgery at Annamalai University and SRM University. He was Associate Editor of the *Indian Journal of Surgery*, Editor of the *Journal of Neonatal Surgery*, Editor-in-Chief of the *Journal of International Medical Sciences Academy* and Editor of *Yakkai*, a vernacular (Tamil) Health Magazine. He is an editor of *IAPS Textbook of Pediatric Surgery*. He has authored 120 journal articles and 14 chapters in textbooks with an h-index of 22. His articles are cited in more than 99 popular textbooks. He was President of the Association of Tamilnadu and Pondicherry Pediatric Surgeons and Founder Convener of Community Oriented Pediatric Surgeons. He is a Tamil poet and has authored 3 literary books in Tamil. His name is eponymously associated with ectopic testis within Spigelian hernia (Raveenthiran Syndrome).

Yogesh Kumar Sarin (Editor)

Dr. Yogesh Kumar Sarin is Director Professor and Head of the Department of Pediatric Surgery at Lady Hardinge Medical College, New Delhi. Previously he served as Head of Pediatric Surgery at Maulana Azad Medical College, Delhi. He is also qualified MBA in health care. He is recipient of many awards and honors including Delhi State Award for Doctors for the year 2012-13. He is a visiting Professor at many universities/ teaching hospitals in India and abroad. He has to his credited 300 publications with an h-index of 19. He authored a monograph on Wilms' Tumor, besides several book chapters. He is editor-in-chief of the *Journal of Neonatal Surgery* and editorial board member of more than a dozen journals. He has been a reviewer for 76 medical journals. He was the Secretary-cum treasurer (2005-07) and President of Indian Association of Pediatric Surgeons (2021-22). He is presently Secretary of Indian Child Abuse, Neglect and Child Labor (ICANCL) group of Indian Academy of Pediatrics. He is the master mind behind the *Annual Updates in Pediatric Surgery* at Maulana Azad Medical College which is very popular among Pediatric Surgical trainees.

Govindarajan Krishnakumar (Assistant Editor)

Dr. Krishnakumar is Professor of Pediatric Surgery at the Jawaharlal Institute of Postgraduate Medical Education and Research, Pondicherry, India. He is a Fellow of several prestigious organizations including the American College of Surgeons, International College of Surgeons, Association of Surgeons of India, Indian Association of GI Endoscopic Surgeons, Indian Association of Pediatric Surgeons and Indian Society of Pediatric Urology. He has published more than 50 publications, 5 book chapters. He is reviewer for several prestigious journals.

Ananda Kumara Lamaheewage (Editorial Board Member)

Dr Lamaheewage is Senior Consultant Paediatric Surgeon at Lady Ridgeway Hospital, Colombo, Sri Lanka. He is President of the Sri Lankan Association of Pediatric Surgeons. He is a member of World Federation of Associations of Pediatric surgeons, SAARC Federation of Pediatric surgeons and College of Pediatricians of Sri Lanka. He is a Founder member of the Global Initiative for Children's Surgery.

Ashish Lal Shrestha (Editorial Board Member)

Dr. Ashish Lal Shrestha is Associate Professor and Head of the Department of Pediatric and Neonatology, Kathmandu Medical College and Teaching Hospital, Kathmandu, Nepal. He is Consultant Pediatric and Neonatal Surgeon, Grande International Hospital, Kathmandu.

Humberto Lugo Vincente (Editorial Board Member)

Dr Humberto Lugo Vincente is Professor Pediatric Surgery and Academic Director of Pediatric Surgery at Department of Surgery, Hospital Regional de Bayamon at Universidad Central del Caribe, School of Medicine at University of Puerto Rico and Ponce School of Medicine, Puerto Rico. He is also Consultant Pediatric Surgeon at San Jorge Children's Hospital. He is Editor-in-Chief of *Pediatric Surgery Update*, *Pediatric Surgery Handbook* and *Boletin Association Medicine PR*. He was Chairman of American College of Surgeons (Puerto Rico Chapter). He is editorial board member of several journals. He was Guest Editor of *Seminars in Pediatric Surgery*. He is the Founding Member "Zonamd.com". He has authored 56 research articles and several book chapters. He is reviewer of many leading pediatric journals. He is recipient of several awards including Doctor of the Year – Centro Medico San Pablo 1995. He was the first to introduce pediatric laparoscopy in Puerto Rico. Painting is his hobby and he has conducted several Oil-Painting Expositions.

Jamshed Akhtar (Editorial Board Member)

Dr Jamshed Akhtar is Visiting Professor at Department of Pediatric Surgery, National Institute of Child Health, Karachi, Pakistan. Formerly, he was Dean, Faculty of Pediatric Surgery at the College of Physicians and Surgeons of Pakistan. He was President of Pakistan Association of Medical Editors (PAME) and is a Visiting Faculty at the University of Health Sciences and Shalamar Medical & Dental College, Lahore. He was Editor of the Journal of College of Physicians & Surgeons Pakistan (JCPS). He is member of the National Bioethics Committee, Government of Pakistan. He is the Course Director of ATLS program and is lead instructor BLS and PALS courses of American Heart Association. He is member of World Association of Medical Editors and Eastern Association of Medical Editors

Varadarajan Kalidasan (Editorial Board Member)

Dr. Kalidasan is Honorary Consultant Pediatric Surgeon cum Urologist at University Hospitals Sussex. He is Governor in Board of Governor of NHS foundation trust, Brighton, United Kingdom. He is also Honorary Clinical Education Tutor of the Royal College of Surgeons, Edinburgh. He is a Member of International Affairs Committee of the British Association of Pediatric Surgeons. He is the Chair of Southeast division of British Association of Physicians of Indian Origin. His interest and eminence in Cricket game earned him the post of Director, Board of Sussex Cricket Limited.

Mohamed A Baky Fahmy (Editorial Board Member)

Dr. Mohamed Baky Fahmy is Emeritus professor and Head of Pediatric Surgery at Faculty of Medicine for Girls, Al Azher University, Egypt. He is Editor-in-Chief, Journal of Pediatric Diseases. He is a Visiting professor to University of Leipzig. He is a Member of the World Association of Medical Editors (WAME). He was Secretary General of Egyptian Pediatric Surgical Association (EPSA). He has edited 6 monographs on pediatric urological disorders. After Cullen, he is the only scientist who published a monograph on umbilicus and its disorders.

Naeem Khan (Editorial Board Member)

Prof Naeem Khan is the senior most pediatric surgeon of Pakistan. He had worked in three different continents namely Asia (Pakistan), Europe (England, Scotland) and North Africa (Tripoli, Libya). He was Professor and Head of the Department of Pediatric Surgery at The Children's Hospital, Pakistan Institute of Medical Sciences, Islamabad and National Institute of Handicapped. Formerly, he was President, Association of Pediatric Surgeons of Pakistan and Dean, College of Physicians and Surgeons, Pakistan. He established a finest Pediatric Surgical Museum at Children's Hospital. He has authored 120 research articles and 7 monographs. He was the first surgeon to successfully separate a conjoint twin in Pakistan. Several of his students who became professors are now retired. He was decorated with Sitara-I-Imtaiz, the highest civilian title given by the President of Pakistan.

Najeebullah Sherzad (Editorial Board Member)

Dr. Najeebullah Sherzad is a consultant pediatric surgeon at Shaikh Zayed University, Kabul, Afghanistan. He is associated with several Non-governmental Organizations undertaking charity activities.

Nara Leng (Editorial Board Member)

Dr. Nara Leng is Lecturer of Pediatric Surgery at Angkor University and is Consultant Pediatric Surgeon at Angkor Hospital for Children, Cambodia. He is a volunteer in Project Batambang and Project Angkor. He is Co-Leader of Cambodian Health Professionals of Association of America.

KL Narasimhan (Editorial Board Member)

Dr. Narasimhan is Adjunct Associate Professor at DUKE Medical School, National University of Singapore, Adjunct Faculty at Yong Loo Lin Medical School and Lee Kong Chian School of Medicine, Singapore. He is also a Senior Consultant in Pediatric Surgery at KK Women's and Children's Hospital. Formerly, he was Professor of Pediatric Surgery at Postgraduate Institute of Medical Education and Research, Chandigarh. He has over 160 Publications to his credit.

Sar Vuthy (Editorial Board Member)

Dr Sar Vuthy is the consultant Pediatric surgeon and Surgical Director of Angkor Hospital for Children, Kampong Cham Province, Cambodia. He has special interest in pediatric orthopedics, cardiac surgery and repair of cleft lip and palate. He is an active member of Operation Smile International, Cambodian Society of Orthopedic and Traumatology (SOCOT), Societe Cambodgien de Chirurgiens and is a Council Member of Cambodian Society of Pediatric Surgery.

Shunmugam Rajah (Editorial Board Member)

Dr. Rajah is Honorary Lecturer at University of Malaya and Consultant Pediatric Surgeon at Gleneagles Hospital, Malaysia. He was the first to start pediatric surgical services in the province of Sabah, Malaysia. Previously he worked at Queen Elizabeth Hospital and Sabah Women and Children Hospital. He has presented more than 88 research papers at international conferences. He is a Honorary Fellow of the Royal College of Surgeons, England. In recognition of his services to pediatric patients and Community outreach programs Malaysian Government has honored him with the highest civilian title *Datuk*.

Tindivanam Muthurangam Ramanujam (Editorial Board Member)

Dr. Ramanujam is Professor of Pediatric Surgery at the Faculty of Medicine, Jalan University, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. He was President of Asian Association of Pediatric Surgeons. He is pioneer in pediatric total parenteral nutrition and day-care surgery.

PDR Sisil Kumara (Editorial Board Member)

Dr Sisil Kumara is Consultant Pediatric Surgeon at Lady Ridgeway Hospital for Children in Colombo, Sri Lanka. He is Chairman of the Specialty Board in Pediatric Surgery at the Postgraduate Institute of Medicine, University of Colombo. He is a member of the College of Surgeons of Sri Lanka and the College Council representing Sri Lanka Association of Pediatric Surgeons.